

MICROBIOLOGICAL EXAMINATION OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN PATIENTS WITH PERIODONTITIS

Shirinova Z.H.

Shirinova H.H.

Bukhara State Medical Institute

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Abstract. According to the results of the examination, the microbiological state of the oral cavity of 60 patients with periodontitis and healthy periodontal tissues consisting of 20 people were studied.

Periodontal tissue diseases are polyethological diseases, the most common of which is chronic generalized periodontitis. The incidence rate among the population of our country and the whole world is growing from year to year. The study was conducted in groups of periodontal pathogenic microorganisms *L.buccalis*, *F.nucleatum* and *Fusobacterium* spp., *C.aureus*, *S.epidermis*, *S.mutans*, *Neisseria* spp. compared with the indicators of the control group, patients confirmed the presence of symptoms of dysbiosis in the oral cavity.

Key words: periodontitis, microbiological studies, *S.mutans*, *Fusobacterium* spp.

The relevance of research. Periodontal pathology, being very common, progresses with age, and by the age of 40, almost 100% of the population suffers from it. Periodontal diseases are often asymptomatic, therefore, for their early diagnosis and prevention, a comprehensive examination and characterization of the state of protective factors of the oral cavity in patients is necessary. [1,2,3,6].

Periodontitis refers to inflammatory infectious periodontal diseases of a non-specific nature. The frequency of relapses and the activity of the chronic form of periodontitis depend on the patient's state of health. [2,4].

Despite a significant number of annual studies devoted to the problem of periodontal diseases, both in our republic and abroad, many aspects of pathogenesis, clinical variants of complications, their timely diagnosis and effective prevention remain unclear, contradictory and poorly studied. [2,4,5].

The purpose of the study: to study the microbiological state of the oral cavity in a healthy and pathological condition of periodontal tissues.

Materials and methods of research. We conducted microbiological studies in groups, identifying the microorganisms that led to periodontal inflammation, and comparing them with the microflora of the dental pocket of people whose periodontal tissues were not infected. For this purpose, 60 patients with periodontal tissue changes and 20 people with healthy periodontitis were examined. Laboratory methods included microbiological studies of oral fluid and

discharge from gingival pockets. The patients were examined at the bacteriological laboratory of the Center for Sanitary and Epidemiological Tranquility of the Bukhara region. Saliva is collected in a sterile tube by spitting in an amount of 1 ml; the component of the deposits of the dentoalveolar pocket was collected with a sterile cotton swab and transferred to a sterile tube with 1 ml of saline solution. The resulting biological material was planted in an artificial nutrient medium on gold. The method of cultural analysis was applied: 0.1 ml of saliva, 0.1 ml of a physiological mixture, as well as a component of the gingival papilla, all this was planted in a nutrient medium. The biological material was planted on sterile agar in a Petri dish: the studied biological material was pipetted over the entire surface of the agar, then incubated in a thermostat at 37°C and identified by type.

The results of the research. Microbiological examination of the exudate from the periodontal pockets of patients in the control group revealed that it contains gram-positive facultative anaerobic bacteria. mutants considered to be a coagulase-negative type of staphylococcus, *S. epidermidis*, gram-positive bacterium *S. aureus*, from *Corynebacteria C xerosis*, *C. pseudodiphthericum*, gram-negative anaerobic bacteria *Neisseria spp.*, *Fusobacterium* species and microbial complexes containing *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Veillonella parvula*, periodontopathogens of the type *Bifidobacterium dentium* and periodontopathogens forming pigment, as well as *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, alpha-hemolytic streptococci, *Lactobacillus salivarius*.

The microbial landscape in the periodontal pocket was studied in healthy individuals from periodontal tissue consisting of 20 people and 11 species of bacteria, 5 types of aerobes: *S. sanguis*, *S. salivarius*, *S. epidermidis*, *C. xerosis*, *Neisseria spr.* and 6 species of anaerobes have been identified: *L. buccalis*, *B. longum*, *L. salivarius*, *P. anaerobius*, *V. parvula*, *B. gingivalis*. Of the total number of microorganisms isolated in the healthy group, aerobes and facultative anaerobes accounted for 38.6%, obligate anaerobes – 61.4%.

Conclusion. In the examined patients, 21 types of microorganisms, 9 types of facultative anaerobes and aerobic groups were identified. The percentage of aerobes and facultative anaerobes was 41.48%, while obligate anaerobes was 58.52%.

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